

Crossing boundaries: A framework for impact and collaborative redesign of school and teacher education

Case Examples

To see how signature pedagogies can be used in practice, check out the case studies we have developed for each example of the different forms they can take. For each case, you will find a brief contextualization and three guiding questions—each linked to a structure of the signature pedagogy. You can see an example of a case below:

CASE 1: Learning Through Self-Study

I've been teaching physical education for a while now, and like many teachers, I want to keep getting better. Recently, I found myself really curious about one specific part of my teaching practice. I wasn't sure where to start, but I'd heard about something called self-study. As I understand it, it's basically taking time to reflect on my own teaching in a structured way. It sounded manageable, so I decided to give it a go.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

This is what it actually looks like in my day-to-day practice:

1. I set a goal for improvement, asking myself: *"what do I want to explore?"*
2. I invite a trusted colleague to observe a few of my lessons.
3. I make short reflections after teaching—either by jotting down notes or doing a quick voice recording on my phone while heading home.
4. My colleague and I meet informally to talk about what we noticed and learned.
5. I also share some of these reflections with my department during our meetings, so we can all learn from each other.

Looking ahead, I'm planning to bring in student voices, between steps 3 and 4. I want to hear how they experience my lessons. Nothing complex, just quick, anonymous exit slips with simple prompts like: *"What I liked most today was... because..."*, *"What I liked least today was... because..."* Later, I might even organize group interviews with students, led by another teacher, to dig a little deeper.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

More than anything, this process has helped me pause and think about my practice. It's pushed me to ask questions I don't always take time for during a busy week. I've also realized how powerful it is to talk with others about teaching, through real, ongoing conversations.

By looking closely at my own lessons and talking them through with someone else, I've deepened my understanding, not just of the topic I started with, but of my whole teaching approach. I'm learning how to adapt and how to be more intentional in what I do.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

Even though I started this process to improve one small part of my teaching, it's become something more. It's reminded me that being a good teacher isn't about having all the answers, it's about being open to learning, staying curious, and being willing to change. I'm learning to challenge my own assumptions and to look at my routines with fresh eyes.

CASE 2: Learning Through Reflecting on your Own Teaching Stories

I'm a very committed teacher educator with almost 20 years of experience. For me teaching is about being honest and transparent, being knowledgeable and prepared. It is about creating a space for your students to learn and grow as persons. My evolving teaching philosophy is informed by one core statement: "I want to educate critical, adaptative and reflective physical education teachers". One key aspect to enact this philosophy is by challenging preservice teachers (PSTs) to be critical and reflective with their own teaching stories.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Overall, PSTs are asked to "look back" on their previous teaching experiences, "scan" for potential scenarios where some ism-s¹ were present, "make sense" and reflect on those scenarios, and "propose" socially just alternatives (e.g., update teaching resources, groupings, etc.). This reflective process aimed to help them identify potential areas for improvement and deepen their understanding of how to integrate social justice principles into their teaching. PSTs engaged with and reflected on their school placement stories, and co-created case studies based on those lived experiences. Some visual case studies are used and shared with PSTs to provoke and prompt this thinking process. [All of them can be accessed here.](#)

What does this help they learn? (Deep Structure)

Strategies such as the "look back approach" and self-reflection on past actions or designs enhance PSTs' awareness and increase their ability to identify social injustices that they had previously overlooked. PSTs developed the ability to think critically and reflexively and to be sensitive to their own and others' lived experiences as they both challenge and develop their beliefs about teaching and learning. That was done in the weekly discussions as part of the small learning communities.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

Autobiographical pedagogies (e.g. "look back approach"), highlights the necessity of being accompanied by pedagogies of care, as it deals with sensitive topics where PSTs learn to analyse themselves and reshape their identities by modifying past habits (some of them quite strongly and unconsciously ingrained). PSTs emphasised how these pedagogies have challenged their own beliefs about how they taught and how they should have taught to include all learners. They also stressed that such reflections are only possible when the pedagogy is implemented with a foundation of care. As a teacher educator, I need to be able to create that safe and democratic space where the PSTs, feel respected and empowered to be self-critical and learn from their own teaching stories.

CASE 3: Developing a Vision – what’s my philosophy?

As a teacher educator, I together with my colleagues create tasks (can be part of a written exam) where we want the students to reason about their future profession. For example, in one course/module (in the fourth year of five) the task is that the students should create their own philosophy for how to implement or work with the field *Movement and dance*.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

In the example, the task is for the students to reflect and discuss how they in their future profession as a PE-teacher want to integrate and work with *Movement and Dance* with their students. They are to use all experiences throughout the whole PETE program including those they may have gained if they had the opportunity to teach dance within the school-placement periods. Thereby they get a chance to look back and reflect on how *Movement and Dance* have been presented within the program, what forms of dance they have met (cultural, creative and training) and how the teachers have created learning environments for them as students but also for them as student teachers.

The progression of the exam is that the students submit their own text but will have a chance to discuss it in a smaller group (about 5-6 students). Everyone in the group reads the texts, but each one also gets assigned one text to read as a “critical friend”. In the seminar, the critical friend presents the text for the group and then leads a conversation with the author asking (critical) questions to give the author a chance to elaborate around the text. After the conversation, the other students are also invited to pose questions and finally the teacher wraps it up, often by adding something that the student needs to change with the text in order to pass.

What does this help the student to learn? (Deep Structure)

By looking back, the PETE-students get a chance to see and reflect on their own progression over the four years that they have been studying, both when it comes to their own movement ability but also and possibly even greater how they have developed as teachers. They are “forced” to reflect upon the learning activities – *what happened* – their experiences – *how did it feel* – and in conclusion – *what have I learnt*. Hopefully, they have developed insights on what kind of knowledge *Movement and Dance* can support but also how they can create these learning arenas as future teachers. These reflections, together with insights from reviewing the literature, and the discussions in class will be a good base for forming their own philosophy of (in this case) *Movement and Dance*.

What have the students learned about their underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

With this assignment, the students have to take a stand on Why, What and How to teach concerning *Movement and Dance*. Many students enter the program with either bad experiences from their own time in school or preconceived notions of what dance is. With this task, together with the practical learning activities, they have the chance to elaborate around what dance could be and, most important, what dance can become.

CASE 4: Staging a situation from my school-placement – Using Vignettes/Storytelling

As a part of a concluding seminar in the second (of three) school placements course, the students are asked to elaborate on a specific situation that has happened during the time in secondary school. The topic of the task is “conflicts” and how to deal with them.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

At the seminar, the students are divided into smaller groups where they are given some time to tell their fellow students about the situations and how they were handled by the student/teacher (the supervisor/pupils) or the school. Then the group are to choose one or possibly merge two stories together and prepare a small scene where they portray the situation. All groups perform their small scenes with a following discussion around ways to handle conflicts and if they actual situation could have been handled differently.

What does this help students to learn? (Deep Structure)

Using roleplay as a didactical tool is quite efficient in order to open up for discussions but also for the student themselves to relive the situations. This is a multilayered exercise where they are both acting as parts of the conflict but also reflecting about ways to handle different situations. To prepare future teachers about have to handle and solve conflicts is a well-known problem within (PE)TE, not least because conflicts tend to be contextual. This chance of acting out different situations give students a hunch though and since it is lived experiences, they will most likely be emotionally involved.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

In the case of conflicts there might not be one way to handling them, but several. This exercise may provoke the students into reflecting about different types of courses of action. As mentioned above, it is difficult to teach about conflicts, one has to experience them to be prepared, but this exercise gives the students a chance to: i) feel the actual situation (getting emotionally involved), ii) act the course of action and with this develop tools in how to handle certain situations, or at least get the frames to work with.

CASE 5: Living the Curriculum / Modelling

The goal was to help future Primary Education Physical Education teachers see the subject through a "new lens", moving them from teacher-centered to student-centered teaching.

Based on this idea, we (Teacher Educators) designed our classes at the university to make the pre-service teachers "live the curriculum", in particular models-based practice, and produce a shift through a "vivid" experience.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Before coming to class, pre-service teachers were asked to read an article on the topic selected (e.g, cooperative learning). In the same line, they were asked to do a search on internet and upload a link of a "source" related to the topic (webpage, video, article...) to the university on-line campus. The last task before coming to class was to review the class notes uploaded by the Teacher Educator to the university on-line campus.

In the "theory" class, all the previously mentioned resources were reviewed and the information discussed to obtain deeper knowledge on the topic.

In the "practice" class, the teacher led a session on the topic selected for the pre-service teachers to experience it as students. In the final step, the pre-service teachers were asked to develop a practical session and conduct it using their classmates as students.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

It helped me (Educator) learn how my students dealt with new ideas and concepts, when trying to make a shift from competitive teacher-centred contexts to cooperative student-centred ones.

I believe that it helped my students (pre-service Primary Education Physical Education teachers) integrate information on a "new way of teaching" progressively. First, acquiring knowledge on the topic through searches and discussions. Second, experience it as Primary Education students. Third and final, design their own lesson and test it with their fellow classmates.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

I (Teacher Educator) have learned that it is not easy to change the views of pre-service teachers with a "fixed" idea of what a physical education class should look like in Primary Education. For some this shift is fast, while others take more time. You need to be patient and provide lots of feedback.

However, I truly believe that "living the curriculum" (at least the way it was conducted), it is a framework capable of transforming pre-service teachers' views and help them see physical education "through a new lens". It works!!!

CASE 6: Independent Teaching in School Placement – Linking Theory with Practice in Physical Education

This case study draws from my experience working with third-year pre-service teachers (PSTs) enrolled in a Physical Education Teacher Education (PETE) program, during the final stage of their school placement in primary education settings. At this point, PSTs have already completed earlier phases of observation and assisted teaching, and are now transitioning into the most demanding phase: Independent Teaching. In this stage, each PST is allocated to teach full physical education (PE) lessons independently across different age groups in primary schools. The experience is intentionally designed to allow PSTs to embody the professional role of a teacher, navigate real classroom challenges, and critically apply the pedagogical knowledge they have developed throughout their academic journey.

How does this look in practice? (Surface structure)

PSTs independently lead PE lessons for children aged 6–10, aligning content with the curriculum and student developmental levels. They manage all aspects of the lesson – from planning and organization to instruction, behaviour management, and safety, while adapting to real-world challenges (e.g., space, student diversity, weather). Throughout the process, peer PSTs are invited to observe lessons and offer structured feedback, which complements the formal feedback provided by mentors and university supervisors and self-reflection from teaching experience. This final stage of placement is designed to mirror the real-life work PSTs will encounter in their future careers. It requires them to move beyond their comfort zone, to take full ownership of their teaching, and to integrate theoretical knowledge with practical decision-making in a dynamic school setting.

What does this help students learn? (Deep experience)

The Independent Teaching stage of school placement enables PSTs to learn how to teach, not just what to teach, allowing authentic classroom experiences. PSTs gain key competencies such as lesson design, adaptation for diverse learners, real-time instructional decisions, movement-based lessons. They learn to reflect on student engagement and learning outcome and use feedback from mentors, teacher educators, and peers to refine their teaching practice; experience the responsibility and autonomy of leading a class and building confidence and professional identity. Importantly, the school placement helps students to connect theory to practice as strategies discussed in lectures (e.g., differentiation, scaffolding, inclusive teaching) become tools they actively test and revise in their own teaching.

What underlying values do students learn? (Implicit Structure)

This final stage of school placement is a transformative moment in PETE as it provides PSTs transition from learners to practitioners, navigating the real-world complexities of teaching PE in primary schools. PSTs internalize values such as professionalism, responsibility, and ethical practice. They embrace a growth mindset by viewing mistakes as learning opportunities and value collaboration and feedback. Through self-reflection and mentoring, PSTs begin to see themselves as committed, reflective professionals ready for lifelong learning.

CASE 7: Peer Teaching for Developing Assessment Literacy in PE

As a teacher educator, I teach various didactical courses within our physical education teacher education (PETE) programme. One of the key aims across these courses is to prepare pre-service teachers to design, deliver, and evaluate learning in physical education, with a strong foundation in *assessment literacy*. Among the diverse pedagogical approaches I use, peer teaching stands out as one of the most valuable.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Pre-service teachers work in groups to plan, design, and deliver mini-units. This includes developing original rating scales for motor tasks, constructing theoretical tests, and designing learning sequences with integrated assessment strategies. For every unit, each group presents their work to peers, who then give oral feedback using teacher-facilitated prompts. This peer exchange occurs in a structured setting where pre-service teachers assume dual roles: as "teachers" delivering content and as "learners" responding, critiquing, and offering constructive feedback. To enhance authenticity, pre-service teachers also evaluate video-based motor tasks individually using various AoL methods (e.g., analytical, weighted), followed by group discussions.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

Peer teaching enables pre-service teachers to transfer theoretical knowledge into practical pedagogical actions. This experience strengthens their understanding of how assessment functions in real educational settings. The process of giving and receiving feedback heightens their awareness of assessment principles and pushes them to consider teaching from multiple perspectives—teacher, peer, and learner. Over time, pre-service teachers gain confidence not just in content knowledge, but in how to communicate, justify, and reflect on that knowledge through teaching interactions. They also begin to question their assumptions about assessment and recognize its complexity.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

By allowing pre-service teachers to co-construct knowledge and critically engage with each other's teaching practices, peer teaching fosters professional dialogue, mutual responsibility, and deeper pedagogical insight. Moreover, it offers pre-service teachers opportunities to practice teaching and engage critically with the learning process—developing not only their instructional skills but also their reflective, collaborative, and assessment competencies, as well as the openness, empathy, and inquiry that define effective educators. However, building a reflective and collaborative culture takes time and guidance.

CASE 8: Learning With and From One Another

In the department where I work, learning with and from one another has been used a common pedagogical approach and the foundation of powerful and meaningful educational experiences for preservice teachers (PSTs) but also for us, teacher educators. When I first came in, I indeed bought into the idea of working in small learning communities and tweaked it a bit to make this learning together piece, stronger.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Every week, PSTs are grouped in small teams (4-5) and are allocated a relevant resource to engage with (e.g., research paper, podcast, blog post) related to the content being taught every week (e.g., culturally relevant pedagogies). Before coming to class, each PST had to complete a weekly submission (e.g., answering specific questions like 'share something from that resource that resonates with your teaching philosophy, in 50-100 words'). Once in class, the weekly submission was first discussed within the small teams, and then within the large class.

What does this help they learn? (Deep Structure)

By working with diverse resources in small teams and responding to focused reflective prompts, PSTs develop habits of critical thinking. The process of discussing their reflections in small teams and then with the whole class fosters collaborative learning (e.g., learning with and from) and the ability to articulate and refine their ideas through dialogue. It also encourages them to apply theoretical concepts to practical teaching contexts, recognise multiple perspectives, and begin to see themselves as part of a professional learning community.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

This experience strongly aligns with my deep beliefs and values on dialogue, critical reflection, and the creation of spaces where PSTs can safely articulate and discuss ideas and develop their own identities as teachers. Facilitating these weekly engagements has reaffirmed my commitment to democratic, relational and participatory approaches to teacher education, where learning is co-constructed and shaped by diverse voices. It has also highlighted my belief in modelling some practices I hope PSTs will take into their future classrooms.

CASE 9: Learning Through Adaptation – Rethinking How I Teach Future PE Teachers

As a teacher educator, every year, I teach a course on model-based practice in our PETE program. In this course, students are required to work in small groups to select one instructional model—such as Sport Education, Cooperative Learning, or Teaching Personal and Social Responsibility—and develop a theoretical presentation and a practical lesson demonstration based on that model. Over the years, I noticed that each group of students came with different experiences, expectations, and confidence levels, while I kept the course structure mostly the same. To address this challenge, I decided to use a framework called Learning Through Action to revise the course design based on student feedback.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

At the end of each semester, I collected open-ended reflections from pre-service teachers about their experiences with the group project. I carefully analyzed their feedback to see what worked well, what didn't, and what could be improved. Based on this analysis, I made iterative adjustments for the next cohort's experience. For example:

- When students expressed feeling unprepared for the practical session, I implemented structured peer-teaching sessions where they could practice their lesson plans and receive constructive feedback before presenting.
 - When students reported that some group members weren't contributing equally, I created specific roles for each team member and made individual accountability clear.
 - When students requested more realistic contexts, I incorporated short field visits and peer observations during teaching practice.
- Each version of the course became a living document, constantly shaped by the insights gained from my previous students.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

This process has helped me understand that learning to teach is not a linear journey. By treating each class as a unique context and paying close attention to student feedback, I have developed a deeper understanding of how model-based instruction is received and interpreted by learners. I now see curriculum planning as a teamwork effort. I do not impose my plan on students; instead, we work on it together. The Learning Through Action framework has shown me that each semester is a cycle of planning, teaching, reflecting, and revising, with students involved at every step.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

This journey has strengthened my belief in being responsive, reflective, and respectful. I used to think of the curriculum as fixed; now, I see it as a flexible practice that can adapt to changing needs. This experience has also made me more open and honest as a teacher educator. By welcoming feedback and showing that I am also learning and growing, I have created a more open and engaging learning environment. My students now see reflective practice not only as something I teach but also as something I practice myself.